

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14497141

Credit Management in the Banking Sector and Economic Growth in Nigeria

Christian I. Nmor; Andrew E.O Erhijakpor & Casmir C. Osuji,

Department of Banking and Finance,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study is carried out to examine credit management (CM) in the banking sector and economic growth in Nigeria". The objective of this study is to examine the effect of credit management in the banking sector on the economic growth in Nigeria from 1994 – 2023. Using the panel data approach, the study covers the twenty (22) deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria out of which a sample size of ten (10) DMBs were used. The independent variable, credit management was proxy by bank credit to private sector (BCPS), bank credit to government sector (BCGS), exchange rate (EXCR), interest rate (INTR), inflation rate (INFR) and contingent liabilities (CNTL) while the dependent variable, economic growth was proxy by gross domestic product (GDP). The data for statistical analysis were sourced from the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin. The statistical tool for data analysis is ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). Hypothesis testing was done using linear regression through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Findings showed BCPS and BCGS have strong positive significant effect on GDP while EXCR, INTR, INFR and CNTL have strong negative significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria within a significant level of 0.05. It was therefore concluded that significantly credit management in the banking sector affected economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the conclusion above, the following recommendations were made: the banking sector should endeavour to put in place measures that help increase their volume of credit to the private and government sector to boost productivity; managers of DMBs should employ lending measures that increase their gross domestic product; the bank credit to investors should be strategically managed in such a way that will attract borrowers and as well not having negative effect on the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: credit management, bank deposits, credits to the private sector, inflation, exchange rate.

INTRODUCTION

Credit management (CM) is the process of extending credit, establishing its conditions, collecting credit when it is owed, and making sure that the company's credit policy is followed, among other credit-related tasks. A bank's or company's objective in CM is to increase profits and revenues by lowering financial risks and promoting sales (Ajugwe, 2024). Therefore, the idea of credit management offers a broader perspective on the contribution of the banking industry to economic expansion. Place a Deposit Banks are trusted with depositors' money. Banks typically use these funds to conduct business. Since the funds are owned by the clients, a program for their management must be in place. The programme must constantly address three basic objectives: liquidity, safety and income.

One of the most challenging tasks facing banks worldwide is CM, which is particularly evident in the case of Nigeria as, throughout the country's banking history, inadequate credit management has been identified as a primary cause of bank failures. Accordingly, bad loans accumulated in these banks' records due to inefficient lending (Ajugwe, 2024).

Due to numerous banks' unrecoverable loans and advances, the amount of non-performing loans (NPLs) in their accounts has skyrocketed. Banks and other stakeholders are now concerned about this situation. CM and Bank Performance of Listed Banks in Nigeria, published in 2015, found that the ratio of bad debt to non-performing loans has no appreciable detrimental impact on Nigerian banks' performance (Okafor, Ezeaku, & Ugwuegbe, 2016; Kagoyire & Shukla, 2016; Nwanna & Oguezue, 2017).

Increased financial irregularities, bank difficulty, NPLs, insolvency, and the impending financial system collapse recently explained the firms and the business community's need for a complete economic recovery. According to these studies, bank loans and advances have a negatively impacted economic performance (Swamy & Dharani, 2018; Karimo & Ogbonna, 2017; Ihemeje & Ikwuagwu, 2016; Uremadu, 2016 and Nyasha & Odhiambo, 2018).

Poor CM has been blamed for reported cases of crisis in the banking industry, claim Ogunlade and Oseni (2018). Bad and doubtful loans can increase progressively in banks' annual reports, according to several research (Uremadu, 2016; Taiwo, Ucheaga, Achugamonu, Adetiloye, Okoye, Agwu, 2017; Nyasha, & Odhiambo, 2018), which suggests that the credit component of the banks' portfolio is not being adequately managed. Every year, a large number of them were writing off enormous sums of debt, which also indicated certain problems with their ability to continue as a going concern that had to do with how they handled credit and finances. It should be emphasized once more that a large number of banks have made advances and loans that are unrecoverable, which has led to increases in nonperforming loans (NPLs) in their accounts. Statistics show that as of the middle of 2017, 14 banks had N177.3 billion in problematic loans. This undesirable situation is foreboding the economy's investment (Taiwo et al., 2017 and Nwanna & Oguezue, 2017).

Over the years, the economy's persistent financial crisis has damaged depositors', investors', and even the government's trust. The current study on the impact of credit management on the performance of Nigerian banks and its consequences for the country's economic growth is prompted by the reason why these banks failed in spite of the measures put in place by the regulatory authorities to checkmate unethical behavior. In light of the aforementioned, this article investigates Nigeria's economic growth and credit management in the banking industry. The rest of the paper is as follows. Section considers literature review, followed by the methodology, analysis and discussion and section five concludes the paper with policy recommendations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Credit management includes, among other credit-related tasks, extending credit, establishing the conditions under which credit is extended, collecting credit when it is due, and making sure that business credit policy is followed. Enhancing sales and lowering financial risks are the two main objectives of credit control in a bank or business.

Loan officers and employees in financial services frequently collaborate with bank credit managers. When taken as a whole, the roles help bank consumers understand the bank's financial products, including credit cards, loans, and credit lines. To accomplish financial goals, this entails explaining the various products, attending to clients needs, and offering well-informed advice. Assessing the creditworthiness of both individual and company clients before to granting any kind of credit is another responsibility of a credit manager. Examining bank records, tax returns, earnings statements, and credit reports are all part of this. Good communication skills and the capacity to explain the occasionally complex financial issues in plain language are also necessary for the position. McQuerrey (2019)

Bank loans expansion of contemporary economies appear to be inextricably linked. The necessity of banks is further highlighted by the amount of financial capital needed before any significant economic development can be achieved. Typically, a person's funds are insufficient to cover all of his development-related expenses. Additionally, the saver can lack the skills and substantial funds required for investment (Abubakar & Gani, 2023). Meaning the banks pool the modest savings of people and households, divert them from consumption, and make them available as investment loans. Numerous studies have used

different bank credit metrics. Levin (2017), for example, talked about the connection between bank credit and economic expansion. According to him, bank credit can be sub divided into two: private sector credit and public sector credit.

It has been empirically demonstrated that the public sector has little impact on economic growth due to its propensity for waste and politically driven initiatives that might not provide the greatest outcomes for the general public. Additionally, he defines economic growth as a rise in a nation's level of production of goods and services or national income during a given time period. It can be quantified in terms of the volume of commodities and services produced by a nation over a specific time frame. In contrast to all bank intermediation, Demirguc-Kunt and Levine (2017) stressed the significance of granting loans to the private sector. In a similar vein, Crowley (2017) notes that private credit is a reliable indicator of economic expansion. The well-known private sector credit's contribution to economy may be difficult to quantify because Onuorah's (2017) study identified several characteristics as drivers of credit growth that are mainly un-researched.

In the literature, theories underpinning this type of work are basically located in any of credit risk theory (CRT), commercial-loan theory, loan pricing theory or agency theory. The CRT explains how deposit money bank managers comprehend the idea of credit risk (CR), how loan defaulters create risk when they don't make their payments, and how they should thus devise plans to recoup the loans (Shaw, 2017 & Keith, 2019). The real bills doctrine, another name for the commercial-loan theory, contends that banks face a dilemma known as the liquidity-earnings conundrum. Accordingly, a bank that wishes to serve as a safe haven for all of its depositors' money would just keep all of those funds in its safe as completely liquid assets. The banker would then just open the safe and return the moneys whenever a depositor asked for cash from the deposit money bank. This would guarantee no risk to credit. But the issue with this is that the bank would not make any money (Ahmed, 2018). Because it has an impact on banks' credit lending levels, profitability, and competitiveness in the market, commercial-loan theory is crucial to the management of deposit money institutions. Because it attempts to explain how banks' credit lending impacts deposit money banks' profitability, this theory is pertinent to the study (Igbe, 2019).

According to Stieglitz and Weiss's loan pricing theory from 1981, deposit money institutions may create adverse selection issues if they set interest rates too high since high-risk borrowers may be ready to accept these exorbitant rates. In an effort to maximize interest income, DMBs frequently establish high interest rates. By their propensity to undertake extremely risky projects or investments, borrowers of these high interest loans may exhibit moral hazard behavior after receiving the loans (Tchankova, 2018). Since loan pricing has an impact on banks' CR, profitability, and competitiveness in the market, it is crucial to the management of deposit money institutions. This theory aims to explain how credit risk impacts deposit money institutions' profitability, which makes it pertinent to the study (Igbe, 2019). Conflicts of interest arising from principal agent relationships between deposit money bank owners and management, as well as between bank debtors and owners, are causing agency costs for the bank as the credit risk of these agency conflicts is transferred to profitability, according to the theory developed by Jensen & Meckling (1976). Agency theory is relevant because it can help DMBs establish a foundation and recommend standard internal control systems that can help banks reduce CR and minimize credit exposures while remaining consistent with internal limits and prudential standards (Parrenas, 2017).

The impact of CM in the banking sector on economic growth has been the subject of a few empirical studies. Researchers who have done similar studies in credit management (Ephias, 2020; Uwuigbe, Olubukunola & Babajide, 2015; Femi, Marshal & Ayodele, 2015; Uwalomwa Uwuigbe & Oyewo, 2016; Igbe, 2019; etc.) have focused on the profitability and performance of DMBs and have neglected to connect their research to economic growth. However, the few researchers (Odufuye, 2017; Nwanna & Oguezie, 2017; and Orimogunje, 2019) who thought that credit management was relevant to growth already had some gaps in their studies because they only looked at the years up to 2017. Therefore, by broadening the study's focus to 2019 and considering the potential effects that proper bank credit management may have on Nigeria's economic growth, this study has filled a gap in the literature.

III. METHODS

3.1 The Model

The study adopted Olawumi, Lateef and Oladeji (2017) model on a causality analysis of financial deepening and bank performance in Nigeria. Their model was given as:

$$\text{PRFT (PBT)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{FD (M}_2/\text{GDP)} + \beta_2 \text{RCPGDP} + \beta_3 \text{RDLGDP} + \mu \dots \text{eqn 1}$$

Where;

PRFT=Profitability, **PBT**=Profit before interest and tax, **FDM/GDP**=Ratio of money supply (M2) GDP, **RCPGDP**=Ratio of credits of Private Sector (CPS) – GDP, **RDLGDP**=Ratio of deposit liability – GDP, **GDP**=Gross Domestic Products at current basic prices, β_0 = Intercept or Constant Coefficients (the constant term), $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ =Coefficients of the parameter estimates of the independent variable, μ =Error Term
In this study, the above model has been modified to suit the variables of this study. Therefore, the re-modified model is stated as:

$$\text{ECG/GDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{NPLR/GDP} + \beta_2 \text{LTAR/GDP} + \beta_3 \text{LLPR/GDP} + \beta_4 \text{INTR/GDP} + \beta_5 \text{INFR/GDP} + \beta_6 \text{TLADR/GDP} + \mu \dots \text{eqn 2}$$

Where: **ECG/GDP**=Economic Growth to GDP, **BCPS/GDP**=Bank CPS (% GDP), **BCGS/GDP** =Bank Credit to Government Sector to (% GDP), **EXCR/GDP**=Exchange Rate (% GDP), **INTR/GDP**=Interest Rate (% GDP), **INFR/GDP**=Inflation Rate (% GDP), **CNTL/GDP**=Contingent Liabilities (% GDP), **GDP**=Gross Domestic Product, β_0 =Intercept or Constant coefficients (the constant term), $\beta_1 - \beta_6$ = Coefficients of the parameter estimates of the independent variables, μ =Error Term

Explicitly, to fit the model in ARDL form, the form is given as:

$$\text{InECG/GDP}_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_{nt-i} = \text{InECG/GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{ni}=01 \text{BCPS/GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{nt-I}=02 \text{BCGS/GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{nti}=03 \text{EXCR /GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{ni}=04 \text{InINTR/GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{ni}=05 \text{InINFR/GDP}_{t-i} + \sum \delta_{ni}=06 \text{InCNTL/GDP}_{t-i} + \mu \dots \text{3}$$

Where: $\beta_0, \beta_1 - \beta_6$ = Short-run coefficients, $\delta_1 - \delta_6$ = Long-run coefficients; μ_t = The error term with the usual properties.

The difference between the two models is that the study model adopted Economic Growth to GDP (ECG/GDP) as the dependent variable whereas Olawumi, *et al* (2017) model adopted profit before tax (PBIT) as its dependent variable. Another uniqueness is that it included bank CPS, bank CGS, exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate as well as contingent liabilities which were not adopted in Olawumi, *et al* (2017) model.

We expected that all the independent variables except inflation will have a direct and positive relationship with the dependent variable. That is, 1% increases in any independent variables will result to a corresponding increase in the dependent variable except inflation rate. This can be expressed mathematically as: β_1 and $\beta_2 > 0$ while $\beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ and $\beta_6 < 0$

3.2 The Data

The data for the study is from the CBN Statistical bulletin for the selected indicators.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The following data presented below were gotten from annual reports of the banks under study. The data is presented below:

Table 4.1 Average financial indicators of credit management in Nigeria

Years	BCPS %	BCGS %	EXCR %	INTR %	INFR %	CNTL %	GDP ₦
2023	20.14	30.54	26.75	25.81	15.75	7.11	5,117,952.00
2022	21.49	45.49	19.78	21.33	14.67	6.12	3,000,945.78
2021	20.36	20.36	19.90	20.76	14.39	6.78	2,094,676.55
2020	24.45	24.45	17.18	17.25	14.28	6.71	2,053,001.84
2019	20.82	20.82	16.81	15.81	14.11	6.67	2,027,512.30
2018	19.84	49.84	16.59	24.56	14.09	6.07	2,123,896.82
2017	19.48	19.48	17.90	21.94	14.08	5.97	1,982,669.74
2016	19.55	19.55	19.39	20.55	14.05	4.79	1,833,645.51
2015	17.84	17.84	18.15	15.69	14.02	3.81	1,687,905.91
2014	29.77	39.77	18.30	21.76	14.00	4.11	1,394,696.60
2013	20.14	20.14	16.55	17.81	13.55	3.19	1,908,805.12
2012	21.49	21.49	19.28	19.33	12.28	4.25	1,827,969.52
2011	20.36	20.36	19.00	20.76	10.00	4.09	1,749,113.29
2010	24.45	44.45	17.18	12.25	8.18	4.17	1,660,355.89
2009	20.82	20.82	18.61	15.81	8.61	3.78	1,573,206.14
2008	19.84	19.84	18.69	24.56	8.69	3.19	1,491,761.93
2007	19.48	19.48	17.70	21.94	7.70	4.12	1,442,451.57
2006	19.55	49.55	17.99	16.55	7.99	4.00	1,396,781.71
2005	17.84	17.84	16.85	15.69	6.85	3.67	1,556,688.44
2004	19.77	29.77	15.80	14.76	5.80	3.58	1,202,819.32
2003	19.00	20.82	16.81	13.55	7.81	3.81	1,151,591.52
2002	20.04	19.84	16.59	12.28	9.33	4.11	1,106,336.87
2001	21.19	19.48	17.90	10.00	6.76	3.19	1,068,611.69
2000	20.06	19.55	19.39	8.18	6.25	4.25	1,019,113.26
1999	24.05	17.84	18.15	8.61	5.81	4.09	978,712.50
1998	20.32	20.82	18.30	8.69	4.56	4.17	942,010.42
1997	19.54	19.84	16.55	7.70	4.94	3.78	905,503.88
1996	19.08	19.48	19.28	7.99	6.55	3.19	879,581.83
1995	19.15	49.55	19.00	6.85	5.69	4.12	848,163.28
1994	17.04	17.84	17.18	5.80	4.76	4.00	816,813.34

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin 1994 to 2023.

Where: BCPS/GDP=Bank Credit to Private Sector (% GDP), BCGS/GDP=Bank Credit to Government Sector to (% GDP), EXCR/GDP=Exchange Rate to (% GDP), INTR/GDP=Interest Rateto (% GDP), INFR/GDP =Inflation Rate to (% GDP), CNTL/GDP = Contingent Liabilities to (% GDP), GDP=Gross Domestic Product

The regression results are reflected on the table below.

Table 4.2 Model Summary (bank CPS and GDP)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.840a	.705	.676		3689312.31294	2.044
a. Predictors: (Constant), BCPS						
b. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.3 Coefficients (bank CPS and GDP)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3737505.547	2789168.971		1.340	.210
BCPS	.032	.007	.840	4.889	.001

a. Dependent Variable: GDP

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.3 shows a positive correlation of BCPS and GDP as the table revealed overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.840 which indicates a negative effect of BCPS and GDP as an indicator of economic growth in Nigeria. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.705 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 71%. The AdjR² is 0.676 which means that about 67% of the dependent variable is accounted for low performances of banks and the remaining 33% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin-Watson is 2.044 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and BCPS. Table 4.3.1b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for BCPS. The p-value of the t-statistics for total assets is 0.001 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Table 4.4a Model Summary (bank credit to government sector (CGS) and GDP)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.747a	.558	.513	4518939.86762	1.415

a. Predictors: (Constant), BCGS
b. Dependent Variable: GDP

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.4b Coefficients (bank CGS and GDP)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1770817.533	3268422.974		.542	.600
BCGS	.031	.009	.747	3.550	.005

a. Dependent Variable: GDP

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.4a shows a positive correlation of BCGS and GDP the table revealed overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.747 which indicates a positive effect of BCGS on GDP. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.558 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 56%. The AdjR² is 0.513 which means that about 51% of the dependent variable is accounted for by total credit and the remaining 49% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 1.414 which shows serial auto correlation between GDP and BCGS. Table 4.4b which is the coefficient table shows significance level for bank CGS. The p-value of the t-statistics for BCGS is 0.005 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Table 4.5a (exchange rate and gross domestic product)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.827a	.684	.920	6732679.57519	2.962
a. Predictors: (Constant), EXCR					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.5b (exchange rate and GDP)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	6963899.424		1.682	.124
	EXCR	-.2620987.377	6161082.681	-.133	.425	.035
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.5a shows a positive correlation of EXCR and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.827. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.684 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 1.8%. The $AdjR^2$ is 0.920 which means that about 92% of the dependent variable is accounted for by EXCR and the remaining 8% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and EXCR. Table 5b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for EXCR. The p-value of the t-statistics for EXCR is 0.035 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Table 4.6a Model Summary (interest rate and gross domestic product)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.915 ^a	.837	.870	8732679.57519	2.962
a. Predictors: (Constant), INTR					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.6b Coefficients(interest rate and gross domestic product)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	8963899.424		1.682	.124
	INTR	-.2620987.377	8161082.681	-.343	-.425	.009
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.6a shows a positive correlation of INTR and GDP as the table revealed overall coefficient of correlation (R) is -0.915 which indicates a negative relationship between INTR and GDP. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.837 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 84%. The $AdjR^2$ is -0.870 which means that about 87% of the dependent variable is accounted for by INTR

and the remaining 13% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between INTR and GDP. Table 6b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for INTR. The p-value of the t-statistics for INTR is 0.009 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Table 4.6c Model Summary (inflation rate and gross domestic product)

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.898 ^a	.806	.799	5656179.57538	2.962
a. Predictors: (Constant), EXCR					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.6d Coefficients (inflation rate and gross domestic product)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	6963899.424		1.682	.124
	INFR	-2620987.377	6161082.681	-2.133	.656	.011
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.6c above, there is positive correlation of INFR and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is -0.898 which indicates a positive effect of INFR on GDP. The coefficient of determination R² is 0.806 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 80.6%. The AdjR² is .799 which means that about 80% of the dependent variable is accounted for by INFR and the remaining 20% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and INFR. Table 4.6d which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for INFR. The p-value of the t-statistics for INFR is 0.011 which is greater than 5% level of significance.

Table 4.7a Model Summary (contingent liabilities and gross domestic product)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.911 ^a	.830	.898	411611.23319	.9621
a. Predictors: (Constant), CNTL					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.7b Coefficients (contingent liabilities and gross domestic product)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22311231.511	5323899.424		1.431	.122
	CNTL	29110987.356	3411082.681	.167	1.425	.018
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.7a above, there is positive correlation of CNTL and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is -0.911 which indicates a positive relationship between CNTL and GDP. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.830 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 1.8%. The $AdjR^2$ is 0.898 which means that about 90% of the dependent variable is accounted for by CNTL and the remaining 10% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 0.962 which shows that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and CNTL. Table 4.7b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for CNTL. The p-value of the t-statistics for CNTL is 0.018 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses involve the test of H_{01} - H_{04} for the banks under study;

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if the P-value of the t-statistics is greater than P-value tabulated at 0.05 level of significant which is less than 95% degree of confidence, otherwise Reject H_0 and accept H_1 .

Test of Hypothesis One

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between bank CPS and economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.8a

Model Summary^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.840a	.705	.676	3689312.31294	2.044
a. Predictors: (Constant), BCPS					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.8b

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-3737505.547	2789168.971		-1.340	.210
	BCPS	.032	.007	.840	4.889	.001
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.9a there is positive correlation of BCPS and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.840 which indicates a negative relationship between BCPS and GDP as an indicator of banks' performance. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.705 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 71%. The $AdjR^2$ is 0.676 which means that about 67% of the dependent variable is accounted for low economic growth and the remaining 33% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin-Watson is 2.044 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and BCPS.

Table 4.9b which is the coefficient table shows the significance level for BCPS. The p-value of the t-statistics for total assets is 0.001 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected and we state a strong negative significant relationship between BCPS as yielded by their operations because the result indicates that high BCPS hinders the economic growth.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between bank CGS and the economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.10a

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.747a	.558	.513	4518939.86762	1.415
a. Predictors: (Constant), BCGS					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

SPSS Version 20 Output

Table 4.10b

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1770817.533	3268422.974		-.542	.600
	BCGS	.031	.009	.747	3.550	.005
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.10a there is positive correlation of BCGS and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.747 which indicates a positive relationship between BCGS and GDP. The coefficient of determination R² is 0.558 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 56%. The AdjR² is 0.513 which means that about 51% of the dependent variable is accounted for by total liability and the remaining 49% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 1.414 which shows that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and BCGS.

Table 4.10b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for bank credit to government sector. The p-value of the t-statistics for BCGS is 0.005 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H0₂) is rejected and we state that there is significant relationship between BCGS and GDP as evidenced in the result shows that the BCGS over the periods was a good contributor to the economic growth.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and the economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.11a

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.827a	.684	.920	6732679.57519	2.962
a. Predictors: (Constant), EXCR					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.11b

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	6963899.424		1.682	.124
	EXCR	2620987.377	6161082.681	.133	.425	.035

a. Dependent Variable: GDP

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.11a above, there is positive correlation of EXCR and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.133 which indicates a positive relationship between EXCR and GDP. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.018 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 1.8%. The $AdjR^2$ is 0.920 which means that about 92% of the dependent variable is accounted for by EXCR and the remaining 8% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and EXCR.

Table 4.11b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for EXCR. The p-value of the t-statistics for EXCR is 0.035 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and we state that there is strong negative significant relationship between exchange rate and economic growth.

Test of Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between interest rate in the banking sector and the economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.12a

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.915 ^a	.837	.870	8732679.57519	2.962

a. Predictors: (Constant), INTR
b. Dependent Variable: GDP

Table 4.12b

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	8963899.424		1.682	.124
	INTR	-2620987.377	8161082.681	-.343	-.425	.009

a. Dependent Variable: GDP

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.12a shows a positive correlation of INTR and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is -0.915 which indicates a negative relationship between INTR and GDP. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.837 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction

at only 84%. The AdjR² is –0.870 which means that about 87% of the dependent variable is accounted for by INTR and the remaining 13% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between INTR and GDP.

Table 4.12b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for INTR. The p-value of the t-statistics for INTR is 0.009 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H0₄) is rejected and we state that there is strong negative significant relationship between interest rate and the economic growth of Nigeria because the result revealed that low interest rate significantly contributes to high economic growth in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Five

H0₅: There is no significant relationship between inflation rate and the economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.13a

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.898 ^a	.806	.799	5656179.57538	2.962
a. Predictors: (Constant), EXCR					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.13b

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11711231.766	6963899.424		1.682	.124
	INFR	-2620987.377	6161082.681	-2.133	.656	.011
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.13a above, there is positive correlation of INFR and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is –0.898 which indicates a positive relationship between INFR and GDP. The coefficient of determination R² is 0.806 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 80.6%. The AdjR² is .799 which means that about 80% of the dependent variable is accounted for by INFR and the remaining 20% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 2.962 which show that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and INFR.

Table 4.13b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for INFR. The p-value of the t-statistics for INFR is 0.011 which is greater than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H0₅) is rejected and we state that there is strong negative significant relationship between inflation rate and the economic growth of Nigeria because the result shows that low inflation rate significantly contribute high economic growth in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Six

H0₆: There is no significant relationship between contingent liabilities and the economic growth of Nigeria.

Table 4.14a

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	-.911 ^a	.830	.898	411611.23319	.9621
a. Predictors: (Constant), CNTL					
b. Dependent Variable: GDP					

Table 4.14b

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22311231.511	5323899.424		1.431	.122
	CNTL	29110987.356	3411082.681	.167	1.425	.018
a. Dependent Variable: GDP						

SPSS Version 20 Output

From table 4.14a above, there is positive correlation of contingent liabilities (CNTL) and GDP as the table revealed that the overall coefficient of correlation (R) is -0.911 which indicates a positive relationship between CNTL and GDP. The coefficient of determination R² is 0.830 which shows that the model is accurate and fit for prediction at only 83%. The AdjR² is 0.898 which means that about 90% of the dependent variable is accounted for by CNTL and the remaining 10% is not accounted for due to some financial errors. The Durbin Watson is 0.962 which shows that there is serial auto correlation between GDP and CNTL.

Table 4.14b which is the coefficient table shows the level of significance for CNTL. The p-value of the t-statistics for CNTL is 0.018 which is less than 5% level of significance.

Decision: The null hypothesis (H0₃) is rejected and we state that there is strong negative significant relationship between contingent liabilities and the economic growth of Nigeria; as seen from the economic growth of Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In the case of the first objective, which sought to investigate how bank credit to the private sector affected Nigeria's economic growth, the regression analysis's findings showed that, as indicated by the beta values of the standardized coefficients, measures of bank credit to the private sector have a strong positive significant relationship with the dependent variable, Nigeria's GDP. This was in line with the findings of comparable studies on credit management conducted by Iwedi, Okey-Nwala & Wachukwu (2015), Odufuye (2017), and Idachaba, Olukotun, & Elam W.G. (2019), who similarly discovered that loans to the private sector promote economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, the Nigerian economy will grow more rapidly the more bank credits are given to the private sector. In the light of this finding, one can confidently conclude that there is significant relationship between BCPS and economic growth in Nigeria. In light of the second goal, which was to assess how bank credit to the government sector affected Nigeria's economic growth, the regression analysis's findings showed that, as indicated by the beta values of the standardized coefficients, measures of bank credit to the government sector have a strong positive significant relationship with the dependent variable, Nigeria's GDP. This was in line with the results of a

related study on credit management conducted by Idachaba et al. (2019), which similarly discovered that government sector lending promotes economic growth in Nigeria. Because it can lower the rate of external borrowing from the global community, the more bank credit given to the government sector, the faster the Nigerian economy will grow. In the light of this finding, one can confidently conclude that there is significant relationship between bank credit to government sector and economic growth in Nigeria.

The third objective sought to ascertain how the exchange rate affected Nigeria's economic growth. The results showed that the exchange rate had a significant negative association with economic growth, as indicated by the GDP. This supported Elijah's (2016) results that the exchange rate and GDP are inversely related. As a result, we would conclude that Nigeria's economic growth is adversely affected by the exchange rate for GDP.

Similarly, the outcome of the fourth objective, which sought to ascertain how interest rates affected Nigeria's economic growth, showed that interest rates and GDP had a substantial negative association. This supported the findings of Adeusi, Akeke, Adebisi, and Oladunjoye (2014), who similarly discovered an inverse link between interest rates and GDP. Therefore, we would draw the conclusion that interest rates have a negative impact on Nigeria's economic growth when compared to GDP.

Similar findings were obtained from the fifth goal, which sought to ascertain how the inflation rate affected Nigeria's economic growth. The GDP showed a strong negative significant association between the inflation rate and economic growth. This supported the findings of Adeusi and Dada (2017), who similarly discovered an inverse link between GDP and inflation rate. Therefore, we would draw the conclusion that Nigeria's economic growth is adversely affected by the inflation rate relative to GDP.

The sixth objective sought to ascertain the impact of contingent liabilities on Nigeria's economic growth. The results showed that contingent liabilities had a significant negative association with economic growth, as indicated by the GDP. This supported the findings of Iwedi et al. (2015), who similarly discovered an inverse link between GDP and contingent liabilities. Therefore, we will draw the conclusion that contingent liabilities have a negative impact on Nigeria's economic growth when compared to GDP. Hence, from the discussion of findings above, it has been statistically and empirically ascertained that credit management has significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

V. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Credit management dictates the financial capacity of a nation and thereby reduces the default rate of borrowers and assists banks to be on top in the loan generating market and foster economic growth. Credit risks emanating from ineffective management is one of the foremost catalysts of banks collapse; however, with effectiveness in management of credits; such occurrences will be eliminated. Therefore, following the results of the hypotheses tested in this study, we can empirically and statistically conclude that there is significant relationship between credit management in the banking sector and the economic growth in Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion above, the following recommendations were made. The banking sector should endeavour to put in place measures that will help increase their volume of credit to the private and government sector to boost productivity in the Nigerian economy. Managers of DMBs should employ lending measures that will increase their gross domestic product in the banking sector. The banking sector should minimise of the Economic growth should be shortened with attractive conditions to borrowers in order to avoid capital tied-down. The bank credit to investors should be strategically managed in such a way that will attract borrowers and as well not having negative effect on the economic growth of the bank and Nigerian economy in general.

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